

A FIBRE OPTIC ACOUSTIC EMISSION SENSOR WITH INHERENT DRIFT COMPENSATION

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SUMMARY: The chirped Bragg grating technique have opened up new ways to measure transient strain events such as acoustic waves without encountering problems concerning the large dynamic range. Theoretical analysis shows that by using the "Chirped Grating Interferometer", CGI, concept with global strain and temperature compensation the sensor would mechanically maintain full sensitivity over global strain and temperature variations. A sensor that discriminates against global strain and temperature variations could be adapted to acoustic waves such as acoustic emission or other strain gradients. Properly adapted to the acoustic wavelength the two chirped gratings of the sensor will experience strain amplitudes of different sign and effectively enlarge the path imbalance of the sensor. Initial calculations for the acoustic application indicate that PZT-performance or even better is within reach.

KEY WORDS: fiber optic sensor, chirped gratings, gratings in fibers, acoustic emission, acoustic sensing, temperature compensation, strain compensation

INTRODUCTION

Background

In the field of "Aircraft Health Monitoring" one major objective is the continuous monitoring and characterisation of damage. Very few concepts of NDT are capable of an in service monitoring of damage evolution. However, the sensing of acoustic emission, AE, is a technique with such a potential and is therefore considered the primary candidate for a passive damage evolution monitoring scheme. The AE technique involves many complex and ambiguous interpretation procedures but does also have the benefit of a sensing range extending out from the sensor and also a limited location ability. Fiber optic sensing of AE is difficult due to several physical circumstances such as small displacements, short acoustic wavelengths and large bandwidth. Previous evaluation has been limited to various Fabry-Pérot interferometers (FPI) since quasi point wise interferometry offers a high degree of sensitivity at a specific location, see figure 1, Henriksson [1].

Figure 1. A Bragg grating Fabry-Pérot interferometer

The full Aircraft Structural Health Monitoring concept includes the monitoring of strain, temperature and damage evolution through a fiber optic sensor network embedded in an aircraft wing structure. In order to secure the sensor function but also to minimise the negative effects imposed by embedded sensors on the load carrying structure, the sensors should be solid and without inherent stress concentrations. Fiber optic sensors consisting of fiber Bragg grating elements seems to be the answer to most needs of smart structures; they have similar structural properties as those of an optical fiber, they do not cause higher stress concentrations than the optical fiber itself and reflectivity and bandwidth can be tailored to a large extent. A major problem with using FPI-sensors has been the need to keep the sensor at quadrature due to the "blind spots" in the sensing range. The quadrature refers to a phase difference of a quarter wavelength between the reflections that result in half fringe amplitude and maximum sensitivity. Much effort has so far been sunk into keeping the interferometer sensors at quadrature over global strain variations.

One of the drawbacks of most fibre optic sensors is the inability to discriminate between temperature and strain. Of the several methods to achieve this discrimination, most of them are based on using double sensors with different sensitivity factors to strain and temperature. A technically interesting alternative sensor concept to overcome the discrimination problem is the Chirped Grating Interferometer-, CGI-sensor, Henriksson [2], Henriksson et. al. [3]. According to this concept the sensor can be tailored to compensate for signals from global measurands such as temperature and global strain and hence effectively be insensitive to that input. Under some circumstances the compensation can even become selective and hence provide a discrimination concept. A sensor that compensates against global strain and temperature variations in the described manor would be very sensitive to strain gradients such as acoustic waves. For a sensor adapted to acoustic waves such as acoustic emission, with a length equal to half the acoustic wavelength, Henriksson [4], the minute displacements involved can very well be resolved.

Bragg Grating Sensors

A fibre optic Bragg grating is a periodic modulation of the refractive index in the core of an optical fibre. Such a modulation forms by itself a wavelength selective reflector, or rejection filter. In recent years this has rapidly become the dominant method to create reflectors inside optical fibres. The gratings are "written" in the optical fibre by exposure to a UV-light pattern. Like all gratings the Bragg grating is characterised by the physical length of the grating pitch,

i.e. the periodicity, Λ , and the effective refractive index n_{eff} for the wave guided mode. These quantities in turn defines the Bragg resonance wavelength $\lambda_B = 2n_{\text{eff}}\Lambda$. Furthermore the pitch of the grating, physically being a length, changes with strain and temperature. Hence the strain and temperature will affect the wavelength of the reflected light. The linearity and the fact that the sensor is a real strain sensor rather than a differential displacement sensor and the integrating length can be made small makes the method very attractive. The difficulty, however, is to separate strain and temperature induced signals.

Sometimes the gratings are "chirped", i.e. the grating pitch varies over the grating length, $\Lambda=\Lambda(x)$. This has two major effects: The spectrum of the reflected light is broadened and the penetration depth of a light pulse will vary with strain and temperature. The latter effect is explained by considering the in-grating position of the particular pitch that will reflect the incident light. The match will occur at different in-grating positions under affected compared to non-affected conditions. Commonly a chirped grating is a grating with a monotonic chirp, i. e. the grating pitch increases or decreases from one end of the grating to the other. The grating can of course be adapted to some arbitrary variation as well. This concept extends the tailoring potential of the gratings even more, not least for sensing applications. A rather new concept of using the tailoring potential of the grating has been described by Kersey and Davis [5], where a chirped Bragg grating is utilised to mechanically enlarge the optical path imbalance of a fibre optic Michelson interferometer, when used in conjunction with a pulsed light source. This is accomplished since the centre of reflection in the Bragg grating for the well specified wavelength actually is shifted along the grating as it is strained. This effect can naturally be used twice in a Bragg grating Fabry-Pérot sensor as illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2. A Fabry-Pérot interferometer with chirped Bragg gratings as reflectors. The concept could be applied as well for signal enhancement as for signal compensation.

THE COMPENSATION

The CGI-Concept

The Chirped Grating Interferometer, CGI, concept is based on a fiber optic Fabry-Pérot interferometer with two chirped Bragg gratings as reflectors. This combination provides a powerful tool for the tailoring of fibre optic sensors. In the combined interferometer configuration of the CGI-sensor the optical path difference between the reflections is caused

by two effects. Primarily, the ordinary Fabry-Pérot interferometer type path difference; strain and temperature changes the physical distance between the reflectors but also the refractive index of the glass in between. Secondly, the penetration depth in either chirped grating changes with strain and temperature. Unless both gratings have exactly the same chirp function this will add or subtract an additional distance between the reflectors.

By utilizing the difference in penetration depth of the two chirped grating reflectors in an interferometer configuration the sensor response can be greatly altered or even cancelled. Differently put, the centre of the reflection in a chirped grating is effectively shifted along the grating as it is affected by the measurand and the amount of shift is controlled by the chirp function. Hence, it is possible to create a sensor with two different chirp functions and thereby controlling the path imbalance of the sensor. The sensor output can be tailored to range from negative signal response via cancellation to significantly enlarged. Figure 3 shows an attempt to graphically illustrate the sensor function.

The differential chirp function that will compensate for the input signal can hence be derived by equating the two contributions cavity and chirp induced change in optical path. This chirp function is referred to as differential since it concerns difference in shift of penetration depths. By subtracting half of this differential chirp function from a "basic" chirp function of the first grating and adding it to the "basic" chirp function of the second grating, the effective difference will be an exact match. The interested reader can find the full derivation in Henriksson et. al. [4]. The principle is illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3. Diagram illustrating the compensation function of the CGI-sensor.

Variations in inherent optical fibre strain and temperature responsivity from plain fibre to grating would enable such a cancellation to be selective and provide a new discrimination approach for fibre optic Fabry-Pérot type sensors. Such variations could either be caused by the exposure to UV-light during the manufacturing process of fibre Bragg gratings or artificially created by using a different fibre in part of the sensor. If the chirp functions of the two gratings are properly matched to one another, the sensor geometry and its boundary conditions, the sensor can be designed to discriminate against either temperature or global strains. Some examples of applications are: strain-, temperature- and acoustic- sensors. The sensor has been given the acronym CGI-, sensor for Chirped Grating Interferometer- sensor. Eqs. (1) expresses the optical path in an optical fibre as a function of strain and temperature variation for plain fibre and fibre grating respectively. The correction factors of η_ϵ and η_T are introduced to handle possible changes in responsivity as a result of structural changes in

the grating. Factors n_i^0 and k_i^m are refractive index and the refractive index dependence to the measurand m for the different sections i of the sensor respectively.

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_\psi(\varepsilon, \Delta T) \propto (n_\psi^0 + k_\psi^\varepsilon \varepsilon + k_\psi^T \Delta T)(1 + \varepsilon + k_\psi^\alpha \Delta T) \\ \Gamma_\gamma(\varepsilon, \Delta T) \propto (n_\gamma^0 + \eta_\varepsilon k_\psi^\varepsilon \varepsilon + \eta_T k_\psi^T \Delta T)(1 + \varepsilon + k_\gamma^\alpha \Delta T) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The discrimination condition is hence that eqs. (1) are linearly independent. If not, any compensation will cancel both global strain and temperature signals. The relevant discrimination is not however between the true strain and temperature but rather between load induced strains and temperature induced changes in the optical path length of the sensor.

Simulations of the Compensation Effects

Simulations were carried out according to a geometric grating model assuming continuous chirp and a strict geometrical reflection criterion. In these simulations the correction factors η_ε and η_T are assumed to be non-unity. These simulations illustrate the compensation effect for free sensors subjected to a matrix of load and temperature variation, figures 4 and 5.

ACOUSTIC SENSING ANALYSIS

Acoustic Sensing

This work is mainly focused on the acoustic respons of the chirped grating interferometer (CGI-sensor), Henriksson et al [6]. Even though the discrimination concept is a very interesting potential in itself a perhaps even more spectacular property of the sensor is the extreme sensitivity to acoustic waves and strain gradients. To optimize the sensor for acoustic waves the sensor length needs to match half the acoustic wave length so that the two gratings will experience strains of different signs. For e.g. acoustic emission the proper length can be rather short, only a few mm. In previous attempts to detect acoustic emission, AE, using EFPI- and FFPI-sensors one major problem has been to maintain the sensor at quadrature, Henriksson [1]. Choosing the compensated design as in this approach the sensor would mechanically maintain itself at quadrature over global strain and temperature variations. The sensor acoustic response, however, is mainly caused by the chirp induced change of the cavity length of the sensor. When the sensor length is adapted to the propagating acoustic wave mode of the AE such that the two reflectors of the sensor will experience strain amplitudes of different sign the chirp will effectively increase the response to the acoustic wave as compared to regular FPI-sensors, see figure 6.

Figure 4. Simulated temperature and strain response for an ordinary FP-sensor with straight gratings as reflectors.

Figure 5. Simulated strain and temperature response for a temperature compensated FP-sensor with chirped grating reflectors.

Figure 6. Diagram illustrating the large shift in penetration depth for a small amplitude acoustic wave.

The Chirp Limitations

Effectively the slope of the chirp function determines the dynamic range of the sensor. If the strain gradient of the acoustic wave is larger than the slope of the chirp function there can form double reflections within each grating that will disturb the interferometer output. Hence the limiting factor of the chirp function is that the slope should exceed the expected strain gradient of the largest acoustic wave. Apparently the resolution is opposed to the dynamic range but there is no definite theoretical limitation to the resolution.

Displacement Resolution Estimate

Approximating an AE with its dominating harmonic, e.g. a sinusoidal wave with the frequency 150 kHz, and applying a rather large AE-amplitude e.g. 1nm the dynamic range can be determined together with the minimum slope of the chirp function. The displacement of the wave is:

$$u = A \sin(\omega t + kz) \quad (1)$$

where A is the amplitude, ω is the circular frequency and k is the circular wave number. The first derivative of the displacement equals the strain wave:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{du}{dz} = kA \cos(\omega t + kz) \quad (2)$$

and the second is the strain gradient:

$$\frac{d\varepsilon}{dz} = -k^2 A \sin(\omega t + kz) \quad (3)$$

Hence the slope of the chirp function K should be:

$$K \geq \left| \frac{d\varepsilon}{dz} \right|_{max} = k^2 A \quad (4)$$

Strain effects on the refractive index are in this context less than the order 10^{-6} and can be neglected. Inserting values for the wave number and the amplitude, e.g. $k=\pi/3\text{mm}$, $A=1\text{nm}$, yields a chirp function slope of about $1.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$. A very moderate interferometer performance even for high a bandwidth is a fringe SNR of about 100. Used with an optical wavelength of 1550nm the resolution for length changes in the cavity is about 1.64nm. Splitting this number for the two gratings each grating apparently has to shift its penetration depth 0.82nm for detection when the sensor is at quadrature. With the penetration depth shifted 0.82nm and the strain field applied the Bragg resonance criteria should be fulfilled just as with Λ_0 :

$$\Lambda_0 = \Lambda_0 (1 + Kz)(1 + \varepsilon) \left(1 - \eta_\varepsilon \frac{n_0^2}{2} [P_{12} - \nu(P_{11} + P_{12})] \varepsilon \right) \quad (5)$$

Keeping just the first order terms in ε and Kz the equation is easily solved:

$$\varepsilon \approx - \frac{Kz}{\left(1 - \eta_\varepsilon \frac{n_0^2}{2} [P_{12} - \nu(P_{11} + P_{12})] \right)} \approx -1.32Kz = -1.19 \cdot 10^{-12} \quad (6)$$

The strain that would generate a shift of detectable magnitude is no larger than $1.2 \cdot 10^{-12}$. When the acoustic wave of that strain amplitude is integrated once the resulting displacement amplitude is as small as $1.1 \cdot 10^{-15}$! This level of sensitivity is for the proper acoustic wavelength match only. Obviously, the sensor will be sensing strain gradients in the material and not the displacements. In this respect much like the PZT-transducers commonly used to detect AE that sense accelerations. However, unlike the more or less resonant PZT-

transducers, the only bandwidth limiting factor is the sensor length. Hence the CGIA-sensor signal can be integrated twice into the true displacement amplitude. For other wavelengths the amplitude would naturally have to be larger to be detected.

Acoustic Sensor Conditions

For the acoustic sensing there are no discrimination requirements. The difference would merely be whether or not the sensor would detect temperature variations. Any such response would easily be filtered out, however, and the sensor function would be similar. The difficulties regarding the acoustic sensor are of a rather practical nature. If the target is AE the sensor would have to be rather short to span no more than half an acoustic wavelength. This imposes problems to the realization of the sensor since the applicability of the penetration depth function of Ouelette [7] for chirped gratings of such short lengths is questionable. Possibly somewhat longer gratings allowing for some overlap between the two gratings would be an option. Still, some response is expected even for short gratings and sensors.

Simulations of Acoustic Response

In the simulation the sensor models are subjected to a sinusoidal displacement wave with both time and position dependence. The simulated responses are illustrated in figures 7 and 8 for a sensor with straight and chirped gratings respectively. The slope of the chirp function in this case is 0.24 m^{-1} , i. e. much steeper than optimized, and the acoustic wavelength is 30 mm. Theoretically the increase in sensitivity for this particular combination is 661 times. The sensor would of course be sensing strain gradients in the material and not the actual displacement. It is an exact analogy with the acceleration detecting PZT-transducers commonly used to detect AE but with respect to position rather than time. This is actually what provides the sensitivity of these two methods; they will both detect second order derivatives of the displacement. For non-dispersive wave propagation these signals would, in principal, be identical.

Figure 7. The phase response of a sensor with straight regular gratings to an acoustic wave.

Figure 8. The phase response of a sensor with chirped gratings to an acoustic wave.

Experiments

Experimental determination of the dose dependent correction factors for strain and temperature dependence of the refractive index within the grating was carried out for boron co-doped fibre. Fibre optic gratings of different reflectivities were examined to determine the dose influence of the refractive index strain and temperature dependencies. Two different gratings of identical period and length but of significantly different UV-dose were subjected to temperature and load variations separately. The shift of the Bragg wavelength in response to the variations was taken as an indication of the dose dependencies.

The results showed no significant discrepancy. For boron co-doped hydrogen sensitised fibres no deviations could be detected. Hence, for such fibre, artificial variation of temperature dependence over the sensor is required to achieve discrimination. Though this is not a success for the discrimination concept it is indeed still interesting for the acoustic sensing concept. Effectively the compensated sensor would remain stable for both temperature and strain variations while very sensitive to acoustic waves. Evaluations are underway to see if fibre gratings formed with other physical mechanisms will perform differently.

The planned evaluation of the CGI-prototypes will involve composite DCB specimens with embedded fibre optic sensors. The fibre optic sensor response to the AE generated by the central mode I delamination will be registered parallel to the signals of conventional PZT-transducers. The relative waveforms and frequency contents from either sensor will be demonstrated together with the PZT-recordings for the same waves.

CONCLUSIONS

To accurately determine the correct chirp function of the sensor gratings each individual fibre would have to be evaluated with respect to photo elastic constants, thermal expansion coefficient and temperature dependence of the refractive index. Equally important is to consider the boundary conditions of the sensing environment. The compensation of an embedded sensor requires other chirps than compensation of a free sensor. The CGI-sensors acoustic sensitivity is not dependent on the discrimination between temperature and strain. In fact, the sensor would be even more stable if both the strain and temperature responses were removed. Then the sensor would inevitably be operational with a stable detectability by keeping the at quadrature.

A couple of comparisons are of interest:

Compared to the best results by previous fiber optic AE-systems obtained by Henriksson, [1], using the same detection scheme and circuitry the CGI-sensor concept offers a theoretical improvement in the order of 10^6 times regarding displacement resolution for AE. If these theoretical figures are experimentally verified they will indeed signify a breakthrough.

Even compared to the performance of conventional PZT AE-transducers the performance is good. So far the PZT-transducers have been outstanding in their very reliable and extremely sensitive operation. The PZT-transducer is actually an accelerometer for high bandwidths and as such it responds to force across the crystal or acceleration. The integrations to displacement resolution is of course bandwidth dependent and not exactly straight forward. Still, Pollack,

[8], claims an impressive PZT resolution of no more than $25 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{m}$. Even resolutions in the order of 10^{-14}m have been claimed, Brüel&Kjaer [9]. In comparison to these values the estimated $1.1 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{m}$ resolution of the CGI-sensor is very encouraging.

The CGI-sensor acoustic sensitivity is not dependant on the compensation. The sensor can indeed be operated with any chirp functions with varying sensitivity. The compensation does however enable a stable detectability by keeping the sensor at quadrature. It was shown in this study that optical fibers that would not discriminate between strain and temperature in the CGI-configuration are commonly available. Hence the compensation for global variations includes both of these measurands. If preferred the acoustic sensing could of course be combined with simultaneous temperature readings if the discrimination is enabled by an appropriate choice of fibre. Shifts due to temperature variations are easily dealt with. Mainly due to the difference in dynamic range.

For a complete aircraft health monitoring system, where strain, temperature and AE is acquired a combination of CGI-sensors appears to be very interesting. Generally in fiber optic sensing the discrimination between strain and temperature is the problem. With this approach however, the discrimination issue can be between AE and temperature variations. This task is considerably much easier since the dynamic range of the two measurands are so different, in the order of 1 Hz for temperature and 100 kHz for AE, and could easily be solved by simple filtering. A system including CGIS-sensors for strain detection and CGIT-sensors for temperature and AE detection holds a high potential to fulfil the needs of a health monitoring system .

The manufacturing of a chirped grating of the required accuracy is obviously very difficult. The compensating chirp functions are close to linear and if the manufacturing process would benefit from this it could of course be approximated as such. However, at IOF, the Institute of optical research in Stockholm, a technique to accomplish extremely accurate and repetitive chirped gratings of an arbitrary chirp function has been developed. Using this technique very long and superstructured gratings are composed by writing a set of consecutive sub gratings with interferometric control of the relative positions between sub gratings, R. Stubbe et. al. [10]. For chirped gratings, the chirp function is basically formed by imprinting the sub gratings with its own specific phase shift as compared to the former prints. In this manor very long gratings with a very accurate chirp function has successfully been manufactured. Attempts to realize the various CGI-sensors are currently underway.

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REFERENCES

1. A. Henriksson: "Evaluation and Development of Fiber Optic Sensors and Systems with respect to Acoustic Emission", FFA TN 1994-37, Stockholm, Sweden, 1994.
2. A. Henriksson: "A Temperature Invariant Fiber Optic Bragg Grating Fabry-Pérot Interferometer", FFA TN 1996-02, Stockholm, Sweden, 1996.
3. A. Henriksson, S. Sandgren and A. Asseh: "Temperature insensitivity of a fiber optic Bragg grating sensor", to appear in Proceedings "Fiber Optic and Laser Sensors XIV", SPIE Vol. 2803, Denver, 4-9 Aug. 1996.
4. A. Henriksson: "The Optimized Detection of Acoustic Emission Generated Lamb Waves using embedded Fiber Optic Fabry-Pérot Sensors", FFA TN 1996-32, Stockholm, Sweden, 1996.
5. A. D. Kersey and M. A. Davis: "Interferometric Fiber Sensor with a Chirped Bragg Grating Sensing Element", Proc. 10th Optical Fibre Sensors Conference, Glasgow, Scotland, UK, 11th - 13th October 1994.
6. A. Henriksson, S. Sandgren and A. Asseh: "Versatile Sensor Concept for Chirped Fibre Bragg Gratings", submitted to Smart Materials and Structures, Sept. 1996.
7. F. Ouellette: "Dispersion cancellation using linearly chirped Bragg grating filters in optical waveguides", Optics Letters, Vol. 12, No. 10, pp. 847-849, Oct. (1987).
8. A. A. Pollock (1989) "Acoustic Emission Inspection", Metals Handbook, 9th edition, Vol. 17, ASM International, 278-294.
9. Brüel&Kjaer, Manual for AE counter system, p 15, section 4.2.1 Units of sensitivity.
10. R. Stubbe, B. Sahlgren, S. Sandgren and A. Asseh: "Novel technique for writing long superstructured fiber Bragg gratings", "Photosensitivity and Quadratic Nonlinearity in Glass Waveguides, Fundamentals and Applications" Vol. 22, "Post Deadline" PD1-1, Sept. 9-11 (1995) Portland/Oregon, , USA.